

acid. Different concentrations of Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pr^{III} solutions were prepared by proper dilution from 1M solution. KNO_3 (0.2, 0.133, 0.1, 0.066 M) solutions were used as carrier electrolytes.

Conductance of different concentrations of solutions of migrants and carrier electrolyte were measured at 31° in Systronics 302 conductivity meter. Distance of migration of different-concentration solutions Cu^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pr^{III} were recorded after electrophorising in Whatman Paper No. 1 using 1 drop (containing 10^{-4} g) of each solution in a Wieland and Fischer type⁸ horizontal electrophoretic apparatus for 1 h at 220 V using carrier electrolytes (i) 0.1M KNO_3 and (ii) varying the concentration (0.2, 0.133, 0.1, 0.66 M) of KNO_3 .

Results and Discussion

It is observed from Tables 1 and 2 that for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} ions, with increasing molar conductances of the migrant, the distance traversed increases, i.e. the mobility increases as expected, and with increasing molar conductances of the carrier electrolyte the mobility of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pr^{III} also increases. When the molar conductances of carrier electrolyte (KNO_3) are 148.88 and $158.54 \mu\Omega^{-1}$ at 31° the salt is about 80-90% dissociated, so the mobility of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pr^{III} are very high, when the molar conductance of KNO_3 is $111.18 \mu\Omega^{-1}$ at 31°, the movement of the ions being greatly retarded by electrical attraction owing to the close proximity of ion at such lower value of molar conductance of carrier electrolyte. Fig. 1 clearly indicates that there is a

Fig. 1.

sharp increase in the mobility of Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pr^{III} when the molar conductance of carrier electrolyte (KNO_3) increases from 111.18 to $148.8 \mu\Omega^{-1}$. However, in case of Pr^{III} with increasing molar conductance of the migrant its mobility at first increases and then decreases. Such sharp decrease in mobility of Pr^{III} at higher values of molar conductance of the migrant is probably due to hydrolysis, as all trivalent lanthanide ions are hydrolysed with dilution according to the equation⁹,

It is observed from Table 2 that upto 0.66 M concentration of the carrier electrolyte there is no possibility of hydrolysis of the migrants. It may be that if the concentration of carrier electrolyte is further decreased there is a possibility of hydrolysis of the migrants. But the experiment could not be performed because of the fact that the migrant cannot be developed due to high dilution of the carrier electrolyte.

It appears that by noting the conductance values of carrier electrolyte the degree of separation can be ascertained, since degree of separation depends on the degree of dissociation of electrolytes. Moreover, it is observed that with change in conductance the character of the species alters and also the mobility changes, so the possibility of separation becomes better. It can be concluded that by paper-electrophoretic studies the mobility of cations are indirectly proportional to the molar conductances of the salt of the corresponding cations and also to the molar conductances of the carrier electrolyte.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. S. K. Bose, Department of Chemistry, University of Calcutta for his valuable suggestion during the course of this work.

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Synthesis of Some Spiro[5.5]undecanes as Possible Analgesic Agents

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Manuscript received 13 January 1983, revised 25 June 1984, accepted 18 January 1985

LEDNICER *et al.*¹ reported narcotic-like analgesic activity in 4-phenyl-4-(dimethylamino)cyclohexanone. Further investigation revealed that some 4-aryl-4-dialkylaminocyclohexanone ketals

possess high analgesic activity. Analgesic activity has also been observed among some spiranes^{2,3}. It has, therefore, been considered worthwhile to synthesise some spiro[5.5]undecanes to examine their analgesic activity. With this object in view 2-substituted-4-phenylspiro[5.5]undecanes of the type 1 have been synthesised.

4-Phenylspiro[5.5]undeca-2-one³ on treatment with HCN and an amine following a method of Shukla *et al.*⁴ gave good yield of aminonitriles (2). Reduction and subsequent methylation yielded the desired products (1). Mass spectra of the aminonitrile gave molecular ion peak at *m/e* 344 ($R' = \text{anilino}$), 358 ($R' = \textit{para}$ -toluidino), and 336 ($R' = \textit{piperidino}$) and base peaks at *m/e* 317, 331 and 309, respectively indicating the loss of one molecule of HCN in all cases with the formation of compounds of the type 3.

These compounds (1) were tested for analgesic activity (Eddy hot-plate method⁵) and none showed any activity at the dose level of 50 mg/kg.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were taken in a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian-EM-390, 90 MHz instrument and in deuteriochloroform with TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on a AEI Barton Mass-30 spectrometer. C, H and N analyses of compounds 1-15 are within the experimental error.

2-Substituted-amino-2-cyano-4-phenylspiro[5.5]undecane (2): Potassium cyanide (0.1M) was dissolved in water (12 ml) and 4-phenylspiro[5.5]undeca-2-one³ (0.1M) was added to it. The reaction mixture was cooled in ice-bath and glacial acetic acid (0.1M) was added dropwise. After ~15 min amine (0.1M) and rectified spirit were added to clear the solution and left overnight. The product was filtered, dried and crystallised from methanol in good yields (Table 1). The aminonitrile showed ir absorption at 2330 cm^{-1} (CN) and the compounds

1, 2 and 3 (Table 1) showed additional absorption at 3400 cm^{-1} (NH). The nmr spectra of 2-cyano-2-phenylamino-4-phenylspiro[5.5]undecanes in CDCl_3 was found as δ 7-7.3 (m, 10H, ArH), 3.7 (s, 1H, NH), 2.2 (d, 2H, C_3) and 1.6 (m, 12H, $C_{5,7-11}$).

2-Substituted-amino-2-amino methyl-4-phenylspiro[5.5]undecane: The nitrile (2) was reduced with LAH in dry ether. The amine was isolated in the usual manner in good yield. The compounds show ir absorption at 3300 cm^{-1} (NH) (Table 1).

2-Substituted-amino-2-dimethylaminomethyl-4-phenylspiro[5.5]undecane: A mixture of 2-substituted amino, 2-dimethylaminomethyl-4-phenylspiro[5.5]undecane (0.01 M), formic acid (0.02 M) and formaldehyde (15 ml) was heated on a water bath for 6 h. It was then worked up in the usual way and converted into hydrochloride (Table 1).

TABLE 1

Sl. no.	R'	R	M.p. °C	Molecular formula
2-Substituted-amino-2-cyano-4-phenylspiro[5.5]undecane (2)				
1.	Anilino	Nil	153	$C_{24}H_{28}N_2$
2.	<i>p</i> -Toluidino	Nil	123	$C_{25}H_{30}N_2$
3.	<i>o</i> -Toluidino	Nil	130	$C_{26}H_{30}N_2$
4.	Piperidino	Nil	137	$C_{23}H_{32}N_2$
5.	Morpholino	Nil	120	$C_{22}H_{30}N_2$
6.	Hexamethylene amino	Nil	95	$C_{28}H_{34}N_2$
2-Substituted-amino-2-dimethylaminomethyl-4-phenylspiro[5.5]undecane hydrochloride (1)				
7.	Anilino	H	100 ^a	
8.	<i>p</i> -Toluidino	H	115 ^a	
9.	<i>o</i> -Toluidino	H	210 ^a	
10.	Piperidino	H	112 ^b	
11.	Piperidino	CH ₃	210 ^b	
12.	Morpholino	H	206 ^b	
13.	Morpholino	CH ₃	145 ^b	
14.	Hexamethylene amino	H	215 ^b	
15.	Hexamethylene amino	CH ₃	200 ^b	

Solvent of crystallisation: ^a alcohol, ^b benzene: petroleum-ether (b.p. 60-80°), 1:1.

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